

SensApp

D1.5 Flyers with project targets and first results and promotional movie

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1. Flyers with project targets and first results

The images below show the front and backside of the flyer produced after the first year of the project (2019.01.01 – 2019.12.31).

Consortium

The coordinator
National Research Council of Italy (CNR)
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Partners

- Vrije Universiteit Brussel (Belgium)
- IRCCS Centre "Bonino Pulejo" (Italy)
- Johannes Kepler Universität Linz (Austria)
- VTT Technical Research Centre (Finland)
- Ginolis Ltd. (Finland)

The group of Pier Luca Maffettone (Department of Chemical, Materials and Production Engineering – University of Naples "Federico II") cooperates with CNR in the WP2.

General information

Start date
1st January 2019

End date
31st December 2021

Duration
3 years

Total funding
€ 3 287 562,50

Programme
H2020 – FET Open

Funding scheme
RIA

Follow the project on:
www.sensapp.eu

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 @SensApp_H2020

Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma by an innovative droplet split-and-stack approach

The SensApp project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 829104

The Alzheimer's disease (AD)

AD is a neurodegenerative disorder that causes progressive and irreversible death of brain cells. The World Health Organization Report reports alarming growth estimates of dementia: 35.6 million cases in 2010 that will double in 2030 and triple in 2050 with 7.7 million new cases per year

The diagnosis

Clinicians make a diagnosis by detecting biomarkers (Tau, pTau and β Amyloid) in cerebrospinal fluid and by neuroimaging.

Limitations

- Diagnosis procedures are invasive;
- Clinicians cannot determine the AD biomarkers in blood due to low concentration (50-100 pg/mL).

Our mission

SensApp aims at developing a "super-sensor" with sensitivity below 1 pg/mL. The super-sensor will detect the AD biomarkers in human plasma.

search for β -Amyloid

droplet-scale assay

The technology

Pyro-electric fields will force the immunoreaction into sub-uL volumes. The biomarkers will be detected through an outstanding droplet-scale assay.

First year results

- Logo, webpage and social accounts for immediate visibility
- First specifications of the super-sensor, with a target sensitivity in plasma below 1 pg/mL
- Plan for managing the data produced by the project
- Inclusion in Zenodo repository of all public project data
<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=sensapp>
- Complete set of functional characteristics and design of the super-sensor
- Plan with clear strategies for promoting the project and for exploiting the deliverables
- Presentation of the project in more than 5 international events
- 1 master's thesis
- More than 5 press releases

THE FUTURE

The super-sensor will allow you to make a faster and non-invasive diagnosis of AD simply through a routine blood test. Highly efficient screening programs among the population will be possible.

This promotional material aims at presenting general information about the project, the consortium and the basic technical and scientific details. The flyer illustrates the framework of the Alzheimer's disease diagnosis, the related limitations and the mission of the project for overcoming such limitations. The column "First year results" presents a summary of the deliverables produced during the first year of activities.

This project flyer is targeted to a broad audience and is downloadable in PDF format from the SensApp website www.sensapp.eu. In order to reach as many people as possible, we will disseminate the flyer using the social accounts of SensApp on Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. The flyer is shared among all partners and will be printed out when the SensApp project is presented at public events such as conferences or workshops.

2. Promotional Movie

Production and publication of a promotional movie, after the first year of activities, was agreed as the key method for an effective dissemination of the project. In fact, such kind of audio-visual material is an excellent dissemination tool for both specialized media and public at large. We produced a promotional movie of SensApp aimed at explaining the project, the targets, the technology, the benefits to the society. The video is created with the aim at giving brief and clear messages about the topic of interest, optimized in a specific format that can be broadly consumed and shared easily by social networks (Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube). As leader of deliverable D1.5, CNR is responsible of this video. The video is shared among the partners and is uploaded to the website of the project www.sensapp.eu and to the YouTube channel of SensApp.

3. European disclaimer

All published information will include a link to the SensApp website where further information can be found. In addition, for all material and publications, the EU emblem will be displayed as funding organ together with the following text "*The SensApp project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 829104.*"

4. Conclusions

SensApp project has produced a project flyer with targets and first results and a Promotional video to be shared among the partners and to be presented at public events to disseminate as best as possible the project activities.